

BARRIERS AFFECTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN SOFTWARE IN SRI LANKA

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Introduction

Background of the study

In recent years, the green concept has become a common interest in the world. This Green concept applies to different industries. When coming to information technology, Green system, Green software, and Green computing are major areas that are considered under the green concept. This paper focuses on “Green Software Development”. Green and sustainable software have been defined in the literature as software, which have direct and indirect positive impacts on the economy, society, human beings, and environment (Salam & Khan, 2017). This study emphasizes barriers to green software development in Sri Lanka. It is expected that people can get a certain understanding of what is a green concept, what is green software development through this research.

Problem Statement

Software and technology organizations face numerous challenges when developing green software (Lago, 2015).

The software developers thought they could easily adapt to green software engineering (Erdélyi, 2013). However, they have faced a lot of challenges when developing green software (Salam & Khan, 2018). This paper discusses what are the challenges involved in green software development and what are the relationships between those challenges. When it comes to the Sri Lankan context the barriers to green software development are not very different from those of the other countries. However, in the Sri Lankan context, there is an extremely limited number of researchers done in the

area. Accordingly, this paper hopes to fill up the identified gap by identifying the barriers affecting the development of green software in Sri Lanka.

Objectives

- To identify what are the barriers that affect green software development.
- To find out the relationship between those barriers and green software development.

Methodology

This study used a quantitative research approach and used an online survey to collect information. All software developers in Sri Lanka are the population and used convenient sampling and snowball sampling to select the sample. This uses multiple regression analysis for analyzing the data and interpreting them according to those results.

Power analysis is used to get the sample size of the study. This calculates the minimum sample size required for a multiple regression study given the desired Level of probability 0.05, anticipated effect size 0.15, desired Level of statistical power 0.8. Using power analysis calculation takes 91 as the sample size of my study. Online questionnaire was distributed among randomly selected 100 Software Developers.

Conceptual Framework of the study

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework
Source: Mahmoud & Ahmad, 2013

Figure 1 shows this drive from the TOE model introduced by Tornatzky, Eveland, and Fleischer (1990).

The following variables are hypothesized as follows,

- H1: There is a positive relationship between Power Consumption and Green Software Development.

- H2: There is a positive relationship between Resources and Green Software Development.
- H3: There is a positive relationship between Green Software Development Knowledge and Green Software Development.
- H4: There is a positive relationship between Green Software Requirements Engineering Practices and Green Software Development.
- H5: There is a positive relationship between Government support towards green software development and Green Software Development.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Path	Path Co-efficient	P-Value	Decision
H1	PC → GSD	0.192	0.003	Supported
H2	LR → GSD	-0.010	0.808	Not Supported
H3	REP → GSD	0.233	0.013	Supported
H4	GSE → GSD	0.610	0.000	Supported
H5	GS → GSD	-0.018	0.534	Not Supported

Findings and discussion

- According to Table 1, it proves that power consumption has a significant (0.192) positive impact on Green software development ($P < 0.05$, 0.003). This is compatible with what is said in previous

research (Kocak 2013; Salam & Khan 2017) where they say power consumption has a significant positive effect on green software development.

- According to Table 1, there was not enough evidence to say resources (LR) (-0.010) would have a positive effect on Green Software development (LR) ($P < 0.05$, 0.808).
- Table 1, proves that requirement engineering practice has a significant (0.233) positive impact on Green software development ($P < 0.05$, 0.013). This is compatible with what is said in previous research (Jannat 2015; Salam & Khan 2018) where they say requirement engineering practice has a significant positive effect on green software development.
- According to Table 1, it proves that Green software development knowledge has a significant (0.610) positive impact on Green software development ($P < 0.05$, 0.000) this is compatible with what is said in previous research (Hilty & Aebischer 2015; Ragheb, El-Shimy & Ragheb 2016) where they say through green software development have a significant positive effect on green software development.
- According to Table 1, there was not enough evidence to say Government Support (GS) (-0.081) would have a positive effect on Green Software development (GSD) ($P < 0.05$, 0.534).

Conclusion

Summary

This study was conducted to identify the barriers which affect green software development in Sri Lanka. 100 Software Developers participated to give their response through the online survey. Five hypotheses were tested. According to the result, three hypotheses were supported.

Major Findings

- According to the data set Power Consumption, Requirement Engineering Practices and Green software development knowledge would have a significant positive effect on green software development. This is compatible with what is said in previous research (Agarwal, Nath & Chowdhury 2012; Jannat 2015; Kocak 2013; Salam & Khan 2017).
- Based on the data set there was not enough evidence to prove Resource and Government support would have a positive effect on Green software development. This indicates if enough resources and Government support is not available, it will not increase the green software development in Sri Lanka.

Theoretical/practical implications

From a theoretical perspective, the application principle to eco-sustainability means that the belief and value system of a software organization is correlated with eco-sustainability (Naumann et al., 2011). This will result in organizations increasing the efficiency of the activity by reducing costs and increasing product quality and developing fewer polluting goods. By identifying barriers that affect the green software development organization can come up with different strategies to face those barriers successfully and achieve benefits gained from environmentally friendly software. When it comes to the managerial perspective, organizations can find a solution to overcome those barriers and achieve benefits gained from environmentally friendly software. As an example, if more energy-saving software is produced, it will help to reduce the cost as well as the system will be more efficient which will lead to the company to be more profitable. Therefore, Green software development helps society, human beings, and the economy.

Limitations and Future Work

This study focuses on only a few software organizations in Sri Lanka. Apart from that, data were collected only from Software Developers, however, in future studies, data can be collected from software stakeholders in various software organizations such as Software Quality Engineers, Project Managers who are involved in the green software development process.

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